

ON AN UNAMBIGUOUS SYNTHESIS OF CAMPHOR. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF CAMPHONONIC ACID

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Trimethyl camphoronate, synthesised by a new method in excellent yield, is converted into trimethyl homocamphoronate by Arndt and Ristart's reaction and camphononic acid is obtained by Dieckmann condensation of homocamphoronic ester and subsequent hydrolysis.

Homocamphoric acid was ketonised to camphor by several methods and this acid was synthesised by Haller and Blanc (*Compt. rend.*, 1899, 130, 376) from campholide, a lactone obtained by the reduction of camphoric anhydride. As any of the carbonyl groups of the anhydride may be affected in the process, the structure of the resulting campholide, from the synthetic point of view, remains ambiguous. This work has been undertaken to effect a synthesis of homocamphoric acid in a way, which will leave little doubt as regards its constitution. It has been proposed to use camphononic acid (I, R = R' = H) as the starting material and to add the acetic acid residue with the help of Reformatsky's reaction. This paper describes the synthesis of camphononic acid.

(I)

Camphononic acid is an important degradation product of camphor and was isolated by Waiker and Henderson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 755) in a very small quantity as a by-product during the electrolysis of β -methyl hydrogencamphorate. It was later on prepared by Lapworth and Chapman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 985) from dibromocamphor, which when oxidised with nitric acid in the presence of silver nitrate yielded a tribasic acid, the anhydride of which on pyrolysis gave camphononic acid. Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 1070) also obtained this acid by the permanganate oxidation of dehydrohomocamphoric acid. These methods of production throw some light on its constitution but confirmatory evidence for its structure has been supplied by Lapworth and Lenton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1286), who had been able to degrade camphanamide to camphononic acid by two distinct methods, the reactions being easily explicable on the assumption of structure (I, R = R' = H) for camphononic acid. The final confirmation of the constitution by synthesis, which had been so long lacking, has now been supplied. We have used camphoronic acid as the starting material. Camphoronic acid is also a cleavage product of camphor and was obtained by Kachler (*Ber.*, 1880, 13, 487) and Balbiano (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1901) along with isomeric acidic residues during oxidative degradations of camphor. Bredt assumed this $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ acid to be $\alpha\alpha\beta$ -trimethyltricarballic acid and this was confirmed by its synthesis by Perkin and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 1169). Unfortunately the yield in this synthesis is extremely poor and the method cannot be employed for any practical purpose. We have been, however, successful in substituting it with an alternate satisfactory method for its synthesis. The above method embodies the general scheme for the synthesis of tricarballic acids by Hope and Sheldon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2227).

Ethyl dimethylacetoacetate is condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate in glacial acetic acid solution under the catalytic influence of acetamide (Cope, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2327) when the resulting ethyl α -cyano- $\beta\gamma$ -trimethylglutaconate (II) is isolated in good yield. The unsaturated ester adds to itself a molecule of hydrogen cyanide and ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- $\beta\gamma$ -trimethylglutarate (III) is obtained in good yield; saponification of this dicyano ester is accomplished by refluxing with 72% sulphuric acid for thirty hours. Camphoronic acid (IV, R=H), isolated in the usual manner, is found to be contaminated with some of its anhydride. The crude product on treatment with aqueous alkali and careful acidification furnishes the acid, which after one crystallisation from water melts at 168°. This is converted by diazomethane into the triester (IV, R=Me) in quantitative yield. The whole of the operation can be completed in a very short time and 100 g. of dimethyl acetoacetic ester furnish 20 g. of pure camphoronic acid.

Camphoronic ester has then been converted into homocamphoronic ester in a very good yield by means of Arndt and Eistart's reaction, utilising the technique recently developed by Bachmann *et al* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 834) in his ingenious synthesis of equilenin. Mono acid chloride (V, R=COCl) of the primary carboxylic group of trimethyl camphoronic acid is prepared by partial hydrolysis of the triester with alcoholic alkali and subsequent treatment with thionyl chloride in the presence of pyridine and the acid chloride is then converted into the corresponding diazoketone by means of diazomethane. The diazoketone (not isolated), on treatment with methanol in presence of freshly prepared silver oxide, yields trimethyl homocamphoronic acid (V, R=CH₂CO₂Me). Homocamphoronic ester when treated with sodium dust in presence of a few drops of alcohol furnishes the keto-ester (I, R=Me and R'=CO₂Me) in good yield. A trace of sodium ethoxide has been found to be essential for initiating the reaction. The ester on hydrolysis with an excess of 20% sulphuric acid yields camphoronic acid, which crystallises out of the reaction mixture on cooling. The acid after crystallisation from dilute hydrochloric acid melts at 230-31°. Noyes (*Amer. J. Chem.*, 1901, 28, 483) recorded the melting point of *dl*-camphoronic acid to be 232°. The ester and oxime of the keto-acid have also been described.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Ethyl α -Cyano- $\beta\gamma$ -trimethylglutaconate (II).—A mixture of ethyl dimethylacetoacetate (100 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (57 g.), acetamide (10 g.) and glacial acetic acid (120 c.c.) was slowly distilled at about 115° from a fractionating Claisen's flask. In course of 8 hours 110 c.c. of acetic acid were collected. The residue, after dilution with water, was extracted with ether and

the ethereal layer washed thrice with large excess of water and dried. After removal of ether, the product was fractionated. Almost the whole of the unreacted dimethylacetoacetic ester and cyanoacetic ester came over as a constant boiling mixture at a low temperature and the condensation product (21 g.) was collected at 140-145°/4 mm. On redistillation it boiled at 145°/4 mm. (Found: N, 5'48. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4N$ requires N, 5'53 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- $\beta\gamma$ -trimethylglutarate (III).—Potassium cyanide (13 g.), dissolved in water (70 c.c.), was slowly added with shaking to a solution of ethyl α -cyano- $\beta\gamma$ -trimethylglutaconate (21 g.) in alcohol (120 c.c.). The mixture was cooled in ice and a cold solution of hydrochloric acid (16 c.c., *d*, 1'15) in water (11 c.c.) was slowly added. It was left as such at the room temperature (28°) for about 25 minutes and then acidified with hydrochloric acid (16 c.c.) in water (250 c.c.). A heavy oil separated out. The oil was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. After removal of ether ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- $\beta\gamma$ -trimethylglutarate was collected at 170°/5 mm. (Found: N, 9'76. $C_{14}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 10'0 per cent).

Camphoronic acid (IV, R=H).—The above dicyano ester (5 g.) was mixed with 20 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid and left overnight. It was next diluted with 15 c.c. of water and refluxed on a sand-bath for 30 hours. The resulting clear solution was diluted with water and after saturation with ammonium sulphate extracted several times with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with a small amount of water and dried over sodium sulphate. The solid acid, obtained after removal of ether, was warmed with dilute potassium hydroxide solution on a water-bath. On careful acidification of the cooled solution and repeated extraction with ether 4 g. of the crude camphoronic acid, melting at 156-160°, were obtained. This was then twice crystallised from water when beautiful prisms, melting at 168°, were obtained. (Found: C, 49'36; H, 6'34. $C_8H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 49'54, H, 6'42 per cent).

Trimethyl camphoronate was obtained by esterifying camphoronic acid with an ethereal solution of diazomethane. The ester was isolated as colourless mobile liquid boiling at 134°/3 mm. (Found: C, 54'93; H, 7'64. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 55'36; H, 7'69 per cent).

Trimethyl Homocamphoronate (V, R=CH₂CO₂Me).—Partial hydrolysis of trimethyl camphoronate was effected by refluxing trimethyl camphoronate (2'6 g.) for 2 hours with a mixture of methanol (50 c.c.) and N-sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c.). Methanol was removed under reduced pressure at 40° and the residue, after dilution with water, was acidified with very dilute hydrochloric acid. The separated oil was taken up in ether and dried over sodium sulphate. The ether was driven off at the ordinary temperature under vacuum. The oily diester acid was next dissolved in dry benzene (8 c.c.) and 4 drops of pyridine added and the resulting solution was cooled in ice-water. Freshly distilled thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) was added to it and the mixture was allowed to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at the ordinary temperature and finally warmed for 10 minutes at 40°. The solution was then evaporated under reduced pressure and freed of last traces of thionyl chloride. A cold solution of the acid chloride in benzene (32 c.c.) was added with shaking to an ice-cold solution of diazomethane in ether. The diazomethane was prepared in *n*-propyl alcohol and absolutely pure ether was used. A solution of nitrosomethylurethane in pure ether was decomposed by dropping on a solution of potassium hydroxide in *n*-propyl alcohol and the evolved gas was dissolved in the usual way in ice-cold ether. The diazomethane solution, thus prepared, was cooled in ice and the acid chloride was slowly added to it. The ether and the excess of diazomethane were driven off under reduced pressure at room temperature. The diazo-ketone (gummy), thus obtained, was decomposed with freshly prepared silver oxide in methanol solution following strictly the procedure of Bachmann *et al* (*loc. cit.*). The

solution, after decomposition, was kept as such overnight. It was next boiled with animal charcoal and filtered and finally distilled. Trimethyl homocamphoronate (2 g.) distilled at $150-155^{\circ}/5$ mm. On redistillation the triester boiled at $150^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: C, 56.57; H, 7.9. $C_{13}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 56.93; H, 8.02 per cent).

dl-Camphonic Acid.—Trimethyl homocamphoronate (12 g.), sodium dust (2 g.), dry benzene (50 c.c.) and a few drops of alcohol were heated on a water-bath for 12 hours, when all metallic sodium disappeared. The cooled mixture was poured into cold dilute acetic acid. After extraction with ether, the ethereal layer was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water again and then dried over calcium chloride. On distillation 7.5 g of the β -ketonic ester (I, R=Me; R'=CO₂Me) were obtained, b.p. $157^{\circ}/9-10$ mm. (Found: C, 59.8; H, 7.5. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 59.5, H, 7.4 per cent). The bicarbonate wash of the above ethereal extract was acidified and re-extracted with ether. On removal of ether about 1 g. of a gummy product was obtained which together with the above β -ketonic ester (7 g.) were refluxed with 100 c.c. of 20% sulphuric acid for 20 hours. Solid crystals separated on cooling, which after filtration and crystallisation from dilute hydrochloric acid with the aid of charcoal melted at $230-31^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 8.6; Equiv., 171. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.5; H, 8.2; per cent Equiv., 170).

Oxime of above keto-acid was prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of the keto-acid with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and pyridine. On crystallisation from water it melted at $189-90^{\circ}$. Literature records m.p. $186-87^{\circ}$ (Lapworth and Lenton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1292). (Found: N, 7.6. $C_9H_{14}O_3N$ requires N, 7.6 per cent).

Ethyl ester of the keto-acid was prepared by refluxing 5.4 g of the acid with alcohol (55 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (d, 1.84, 3 c.c.) for 36 hours. On working up in the usual manner the ester (4.5 g.) boiled at $106-110^{\circ}/8$ mm. (Found: C, 66.5; H, 8.8. $C_{11}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 66.6; H, 9.1 per cent).

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